

Strong localized pumping of water vapor to high altitudes on Mars during the perihelion season

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Introduction

The Supporting Information presented here contains details of the NOMAD SO characterization, including the latest parameterization of the key features involved in the instrumental signature. In addition, the methodology followed during the data analysis is thoroughly described, presenting the study of the saturation of the absorption lines used during the combination of diffraction orders and the improved characterization of the NOMAD SO measurement noise through the computation of covariance matrices. These last two improvements have allowed us to derive reliable water vapor profiles up to 120 km. For this work, a comparison between different instruments and forward models have been done in order to verify the results and the implementation of the instrument parameterization. The NOMAD parameterization is summarized in section Text S1, the methodology used for the combination of NOMAD diffraction orders is presented in section Text S2 and the characterization of the pure random NOMAD SO measurement noise is shown in section Text S3. The method used to estimate the hydrogen escape flux is presented in Text S4. Details of the forward model comparison are presented in Text S5.

Text S1. NOMAD SO Characterization

The results presented in this work were obtained using observations from the NOAMD SO channel, hence, this section will focus on that precise channel summarizing the main instrumental features involved during the data acquisition. The intensity of the light from the diffraction orders (blaze) is defined by the Free Spectral Range (FSR) parameter, which determines the wavelength range in which the different diffraction orders do not overlap. The blaze can be approximated by a squared-sinc function (S1.1) with a width equivalent to the FSR (Liuzzi et al., 2019), where ν is the wavenumber in cm^{-1} .

$$R(\nu) = \left[\text{FSR} \frac{\sin \frac{\pi(\nu - \text{FSR}_0)}{\text{FSR}}}{\pi(\nu - \text{FSR}_0)} \right]^2 \quad (\text{S1.1})$$

The AOTF introduces a sinc-squared function response and in order to maximize the output signal, the central wavenumber of the AOTF should match with the central wavenumber of the diffraction order to measure m , defined as the AOTF wavenumber ν_0 divided by the FSR central wavenumber (FSR_0): $m = \nu_0 / \text{FSR}_0$ (Villanueva et al., 2022). The NOMAD FSR peak resulted to be variable depending on the diffraction order, having a relationship with the AOTF wavenumber (S1.4) and the instrument temperature (S1.5) (Liuzzi et al., 2019). Due to the nature of the sinc function, light from nearby adjacent orders is mixed with the main order signal. In the case of NOMAD, the the left and right AOTF sidelobe wings, responsible of the adjacent orders contribution, are not symmetric and its ratio changes as the central wavenumber does.

$$F(\nu) = I_0(\nu) w_0^2 \frac{\left[\frac{\sin \frac{\pi(\nu - \nu_0)}{w_0}}{w_0} \right]^2}{\pi^2 (\nu - \nu_0)^2} + I_{G,0} \exp \left[-\frac{(\nu - \nu_0)^2}{\sigma_G^2} \right] \quad (\text{S1.2})$$

$$I_0(\nu) = \begin{cases} S_0 A_0 & \nu \leq (\nu_0 - w_0) \\ 1 & (\nu_0 - w_0) < \nu < (\nu_0 + w_0) \\ S_0 & \nu \geq (\nu_0 + w_0) \end{cases}$$

The width of the AOTF also depends on its frequency. In order to reproduce the observed signal, a Gaussian function with a constant width but a frequency dependent intensity needs to be added to the sinc, resulting in a complex function (S1.2) with four parameters variable across the whole NOMAD SO spectral range (Villanueva et al., 2022). The AOTF is defined by its frequency ν_0 , width (S1.6) $w_0 = w(\nu_0)$, asymmetry factor (S1.7)

$A_0 = A(\nu_0)$, sidelobe intensity (S1.8) $S_0 = S(\nu_0)$, Gaussian width $\sigma_G = 50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Gaussian intensity (S1.9) $I_{G,0} = I_G(\nu_0)$. The NOMAD SO Instrumental Line Shape (ILS) can be instead reproduced with a double Gaussian (S1.3)

whose separation varies with frequency and diffraction order (Thomas et al., 2022, Villanueva et al., 2022)

$$\text{ILS}_i(\nu) = \exp\left[\frac{(\nu - \nu_i)^2}{2c^2}\right] + a \exp\left[\frac{[(\nu - b_i) - \nu_i]^2}{2c^2}\right] \quad (\text{S1.3})$$

where $a = 0.27$ is the intensity of the second Gaussian, c the width equivalent to a resolving power of 17000, ν_i the wavenumber (cm^{-1}) at pixel $p = i$ and $b_i = b(i)$ the separation of the two Gaussians (S1.10) defined by the central wavenumber of the diffraction order ν'_0 . The blaze, AOTF and ILS have been characterized with in-flight calibrations during the first years of the ExoMars mission (Liuzzi et al., 2019; Thomas et al., 2022). However, a more rigorous analysis during the science phase of the mission have been done recently, updating the parameterization of the instrument's calibration. For completeness, the most recent NOMAD SO parameters (Villanueva et al., 2022) have been collected here:

$$\text{FSR}_0 = \left[22.59 + 9.79 \cdot 10^{-6} (\tilde{\nu}_0) - 7.21 \cdot 10^{-9} (\tilde{\nu}_0)^2 - 1.00 \cdot 10^{-11} (\tilde{\nu}_0)^3 \right] [1 + K(T)] \quad (\text{S1.4})$$

$$\tilde{\nu}_0 = \nu_0 - 3700$$

$$K(T) = -1.90 \cdot 10^{-4} - 2.31 \cdot 10^{-5} T - 2.44 \cdot 10^{-7} T^2 \quad (\text{S1.5})$$

$$w(\nu) = 20.17 + 7.48 \cdot 10^{-4} \nu + -1.66 \cdot 10^{-7} \nu^2 \quad (\text{S1.6})$$

$$A(\nu) = -1.25 + 1.29 \cdot 10^{-3} \nu + -1.55 \cdot 10^{-7} \nu^2 \quad (\text{S1.7})$$

$$S(\nu) = 4.089 + -3.30 \cdot 10^{-3} \nu + 8.11 \cdot 10^{-7} \nu^2 \quad (\text{S1.8})$$

$$I_G(\nu) = 1.60 + -9.64 \cdot 10^{-4} \nu + 1.49 \cdot 10^{-7} \nu^2 \quad (\text{S1.9})$$

$$b(p) = \left[-3.07 \cdot 10^{-6} p^2 + 0.0017 p - 0.03 \right] \left(\frac{\nu'_0}{3700} \right), \quad i = \{0, 319\} \quad (\text{S1.10})$$

Text S2. Order Combination Methodology.

During the combination of NOMAD orders, a key factor to take into account is the characterization of the optimal altitude range for each order. We have developed a simple method to solve this issue by analyzing the shape of the absorption lines at low altitudes from diffraction orders in where saturation is expected, i.e., orders 168 and 169. To do so, one of the possible characterizations can be expressed as the ratio:

$$R_{\lambda}(z) = \frac{\Delta T(z)}{1 - T_{\lambda}(z)}$$

where ΔT is the difference between the transmittance at the core of the line (T_{λ}) and the transmittance at the wings of the line. The limit of the wings are determined by $\Delta\lambda$ in Figure S1-D. It has been set to $\sim 0.2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in order to take into account the typical width of the NOMAD double Gaussian ILS. With this method, we can characterize two regimes (high and low altitude) separated by a "transition altitude".

1. High altitude (optically thin): Transmittance at the wings is close to T_{λ} due to the low line depth and the measurement noise hiding the absorption line. Hence, $\Delta T \sim 0$ and $R_{\lambda} \sim 0$. Typically this analysis is done below 90-100 km, region where the core of the lines are clearly observed in the measured transmittance.
2. Transition altitude: Transmittance at the wings is close to the continuum τ (ideally $\tau=1$). Therefore $\Delta T \sim \tau - T_{\lambda}$ and R_{λ} gets to its maximum.
3. Low altitude (optically thick): Transmittance at the wings is close to T_{λ} due to the apparent line broadening caused by the saturation. Then $\Delta T \sim 0$ and $R_{\lambda} \sim 0$.

The application of this method to an absorption line at $\lambda=3779.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the schematic definition of $R_{\lambda}(z)$ are presented in Figure S1 in panels A-C and D respectively. We apply this analysis to four absorption lines of similar line strength across the orders 168 (located around 3779 cm^{-1} , 3784 cm^{-1} , 3796 cm^{-1} , 3801 cm^{-1}) and 169 (located around 3800 cm^{-1} , 3807 cm^{-1} , 3816 cm^{-1} , 3819 cm^{-1}) looking for the altitude z_{λ}^0 where $\partial R_{\lambda} / \partial z |_{z_{\lambda}^0} = 0$. Then we average the four z_{λ}^0 obtained, characterizing a transition altitude z^0 for each solar occultation. Hence, during the inversion of a specific occultation, we use spectra from orders 168 or 169 above z^0 and spectra from orders 134 or 136 below that altitude. We also define a "transition range" around z^0 where spectra from both orders are used. To accommodate for the uncertainties during the characterization of the transition altitude and in order to guarantee a smooth transition from the low to the high altitude orders we estimate a transition range of $\pm 5 \text{ km}$. This approach allows us to obtain water vapor vertical profiles from $\sim 10 \text{ km}$ up to $\sim 120 \text{ km}$. A typical H_2O profile in Figure S1-E shows how orders 134 (red) and 168 (orange) are combined during the inversion of the solar occultation 20200828_130241_1p0a_SO_A_E. Dashed line shows the transition altitude and gray shaded area indicates the transition range where spectra from both orders are taken into account during the retrieval.

Text S3. Measurement Noise Characterization

The measurement noise present in the NOMAD SO data files do not differentiate between systematic and random uncertainties. Since we correct the data for the most relevant systematics (spectral shift and bending), our retrieval pipeline is optimized to use the measurement noise as pure uncorrelated errors during the inversion. In order to be consistent, we disentangle the systematic and random components of the NOMAD SO measurement noise using covariance matrices. The elements of those matrices can be defined as

$$\sigma_{jk}^2 = \frac{\sum_i^N (x_{ij} - \bar{x}_j)(x_{ik} - \bar{x}_k)}{N}$$

where N is the number of spectra (altitudes), x the transmittance and indexes j, k the spectral pixels (1 to 320). The element \bar{x}_j represents the average of x at pixel j for all the N altitudes. We computed the matrix after removing the systematics caused by the spectral bending and spectral shift. In order to reduce the artifacts in the matrices caused by the presence of absorption lines in the spectra, we applied this method only at high altitudes (70-120 km for orders 134 and 136 and 100-120 km for orders 168 and 169) where absorption is extremely weak and undetected. We obtained that the random component of the nominal noise accounts for only 20-25% of the total uncertainty, and that the rest mostly contain correlated noise, a systematic component which can be corrected by a suitable fitting of the continuum. A typical study of the covariances is presented in Figure S2, showing a 320x320 matrix with a clear diagonal over a random background with non-diagonal elements (Figure S2-A). From the diagonal of this matrix we obtain the variances that characterize the random noise in the spectra (standard deviation). However this pure random measurement noise is representative only for the upper atmosphere where the matrix was computed. In order to extend the characterization to all the altitudes we scale the new uncertainties following the vertical profile of the nominal error, which includes the effects of the dark current dominating the noise in the lower atmosphere due the decrease of the signal as the atmospheric opacity increases. Hence, the new measurement noise $\delta T'(z)$ for the whole solar occultation can be defined as

$$\delta T'(z) = \delta T_0 + (\delta T(z) - \delta T_0) \frac{\delta T_{\text{TOA}} - \delta T_0}{\delta T_{\text{TOA}} - \delta T_0}$$

where $\delta T(z)$ is the nominal noise at altitude z , δT_0 is the nominal noise at the lowermost altitude, δT_{TOA} is the nominal noise at the topmost altitude (top of the atmosphere) and $\delta T'_{\text{TOA}}$ is the new noise at the topmost altitude. A comparison between the new measurement noise computed with the covariance matrix and the nominal NOMAD SO measurement noise is shown in Figure S2-B and Figure S2-C. Typically, the new uncertainties at high altitudes are 4 to 5 times smaller than the nominal noise. This methodology has been implemented in the calibration pipeline of the Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy.

Text S4 Estimation of Hydrogen Escape

We present here a method for estimating the hydrogen escape flux by the water vapor plume which is based on the approximated method by Chaffin et al. (2017). During its application we have also evaluated the uncertainties associated to several assumptions, as explained next.

In order to estimate the H escape flux induced by the observed water vapor plume, we have averaged all the vertical profiles in the southern hemisphere for latitudes above 45 degrees during the three L_s periods ($L_s^1 = 240^\circ$ - 260° , $L_s^2 = 260^\circ$ - 280° and $L_s^3 = 280^\circ$ - 300°) for each MY. They are shown the nine panels of Figure S3. The model presented by Chaffin et al., 2017 provides a total flux calculated by taking into account the water vapor abundance at different tangent altitudes (from 20 to 120). They assumed vertical profiles of Gaussian parcels with a width of 12.5 km centered at different altitudes. Each parcel has a concentration peak of 20, 40, 60 or 80 ppmv for each altitude which correlates to a specific hydrogen escape flux contribution. We fit of our average vertical profiles with modeled profiles generated using a predefined set of combination of parcels. For each combination we compute its χ^2 . The best combination of parcels is the one that provides the minimum value of χ^2 . The uncertainty of the fitting has been estimated with the difference between the fitted profile and the closest combination of Gaussian parcels available. We obtain a deficient fitting below 50 km which is due to the limit of 80 ppmv in the H_2O abundance imposed by the model. However this does not have a strong effect on the total estimated escape flux. With a linear extrapolation of the model and increasing the limit from 80 to 100 ppmv, the contribution to the total flux of the parcel at 40 km increases only by 3.5%. The increase in the contribution of the parcel at 20 km is negligible. The obtained profile provides the total hydrogen escape flux. The fittings of the average profiles are presented in Figure S3 and Table S1. The estimated hydrogen escape fluxes for L_s^1 and L_s^2 during MYs 34, 35 and 36 are shown in Figure S3. Applying this model to an arbitrary atmosphere, different from that used to generate the model, introduces uncertainties in the absolute values of the escape flux that are difficult to estimate although the variations between them, in which we are focused, are valid. Nevertheless, these results are in line with the estimation by Belyaev et al., 2021 obtained with the same approach and with the escape flux observed by the Hubble Space Telescope during the perihelion season (Bhattacharyya et al., 2017).

Text S5. Comparison and Validation

The objective of this section is to compare the Forward Models (FM) of different teams in the NOMAD consortium in order to verify the implementation of the NOMAD SO calibration. Characterizing these instrumental features is crucial for the data analysis and its parameterization needs to be correctly implemented. We performed a comparison of the FMs used by the main groups analyzing H₂O on Mars with NOMAD SO data. These teams are: Instituto de Astrofísica de Andalucía (IAA), Tokyo University (UTokyo), Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy (BIRA), and NASA Goddard Spaceflight Center. A brief description of each radiative transfer algorithm involved in the comparison and details about the parameters used for the simulations are presented here, along with a summary of the results.

We compare simulations from three radiative transfer algorithms: KOPRA used by the IAA, the Atmospheric Spectra Inversion Modular Utility Tools (ASIMUT) used by BIRA and UTokyo, and the Planet Spectrum Generator (PSG) used by NASA. The results presented in Section 3 of this paper have been obtained from retrievals based on the KOPRA forward model.

- Karlsruhe Optimized and Precise Radiative transfer Algorithm (KOPRA). This algorithm, originally developed for data analysis of the Michelson Interferometer for Passive Atmospheric Sounding (MIPAS) has been already tested on multiple Earth atmosphere remote sounding projects and recently adapted for the Martian atmosphere (Jiménez-Monferrer et al., 2021). KOPRA is a forward line-by-line and layer-by-layer model for calculation of the infrared radiative transfer through the atmosphere and integrates the radiative transfer equation along the line of sight with a Curtis-Gordon approach, taking into account refraction effects in a ellipsoidal surface (Stiller et al., 2002). The line-by-line modeling includes accurate evaluation of the Voigt line shape function using an optimized implementation of the Humlicek's algorithm (Kuntz, 1997; Ruyten, 2004). Line coupling effects, pressure shift, self- and air-broadening of the Doppler and Lorentzian line shapes and continuum emission caused by gases and aerosols are also taken into account during the calculations.

- Atmospheric Spectra Inversion Modular Utility Tools (ASIMUT). The ASIMUT software was originally developed to model the Earth atmosphere and simulate measurements under different observation geometries and instrument configurations. It has been adapted to simulate the atmosphere of Venus (Vandaele et al., 2008) and recently, the Martian atmosphere (Vandaele et al., 2018). Similarly to other algorithms, ASIMUT computes the radiative transfer calculations in each layer following the radiation path and using the Curtis-Gordon approximations. For the absorption coefficients calculation, the single line and broadband absorptions are taken into account along with the Rayleigh scattering. The code allows the user to select different line shape profiles, the Voigt function being the default one and estimated with different methods, including the Humlicek algorithm approximation (Vandaele et al., 2006).

- Planet Spectrum Generator (PSG). The PSG is a state-of-the-art radiative transfer model developed in order to generate planetary spectra for a broad variety of instrumental configurations and observation geometries. As the previous mentioned codes, PSG computes the line-by-line calculations considering the Curtis-Gordon ray-trace temperature at every layer. For the line shape calculation, PSG uses a Faddeeva function as originally implemented by Humlicek, 1982 with improvements suggested by Wells 1999 to estimate the Voigt profile. It takes into account the pressure shift and its dependence with temperature, and the thermal kinetic and collisional broadening effects affecting the Gaussian and Lorentzian line widths (Villanueva et al., 2018; Villanueva, Liuzzi, Faggi, et al., 2022).

In order to ease the comparison of the forward models, a common reference atmosphere has been selected to generate the simulated spectra using the same pressure, temperature and gas abundances in the three codes. This reference atmosphere has been generated with the Mars Planetary Climate Model (PCM) to be representative of the Martian atmosphere during the NOMAD SO observation 20180803_101739_1p0a_SO_A_I (latitude = -64.2° , longitude = -26.5° , Ls = 223.09° , local time = 20.7h). Vertical profiles of the reference atmosphere are shown in Figure S5. In addition, the list containing the line parameters (line position, intensity, broadening coefficients...) used during the comparison have been set to the latest HITRAN 2020 linelists (Gordon et al., 2022), although isotopes $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}_2$ and $^{18}\text{O}^{13}\text{C}^{17}\text{O}$ have not been considered in the KOPRA and ASIMUT simulations.

Typically, the NOMAD forward model is generated as follows:

- 1- A high resolution spectrum is generated in a wide spectral range covering the desired adjacent orders.
- 2- The blaze function is applied, scaling the radiance and differentiating the limits of the diffraction orders.
- 3- The AOTF filter scales the main and the adjacent orders with a squared-sinc function.
- 4- The flux of the adjacent orders is added to the main order signal. ILS convolution is applied.
- 5- Finally, the high resolution spectrum is interpolated to the NOMAD data spectral grid.

The parameters involved in this comparison are: the blaze center frequency (FSR), blaze width (FSR_0), AOTF center wavenumber (ν_0), AOTF width (w), AOTF sidelobe factor (S) and AOTF asymmetry factor (A), which are described in Text S1 of SI. We have selected arbitrary blaze and AOTF parameters (labeled as "test" parameters in Fig. S6) during the high resolution comparison and values from Villanueva et al. (2022) characterization for the retrievals (labeled as "NOMAD" parameters in Fig. S6).

For the high resolution simulation we have selected a spectral range corresponding to the NOMAD diffraction order 170 ($3390 - 3410 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and extended to 3370 and 3430 cm^{-1} in order to simulate the closest adjacent orders. The number of adjacent orders has been set to ± 1 during the high resolution and AOTF comparisons, and to ± 4 during the NOMAD retrievals.

The mean spectral resolution of the simulations are $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for KOPRA, $3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for PSG and $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for ASIMUT. In order to compare the three models, the simulations have been interpolated to a constant spectral grid with a resolution of $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The comparisons have been done with the simulated transmittance of an altitude of 10 km in order to test the models under a strong absorption condition. For the AOTF comparison, a radiance without absorption lines is required to properly analyze the shape of the sinc-squared function. For that, simulated radiance at 100 km has been used. Since each simulation uses a different solar flux, the resulted total flux of the radiances are different, so, in order to proceed with the comparison we have normalized each radiance.

As shown in panels panels 1b-3b of Figure S6, the agreement between KOPRA, PSG and ASIMUT is remarkable. Focusing the analysis on the absorption line at 3400.2 cm^{-2} , the discrepancy between KOPRA-PSG is about $\sim 0.05 \%$ and about $\sim 0.2 \%$ between KOPRA-ASIMUT. We do not observe any spectral shift between simulations in panel 3, meaning that the addition of the adjacent orders was equally reproduced in the KOPRA and PSG models. Some lines appear only on the PSG simulation corresponding to isotopes $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}_2$ and $^{18}\text{O}^{13}\text{C}^{17}\text{O}$ which were not included in the KOPRA simulation. Regarding the AOTF comparison shown in panel 4 of Figure S6, we proved the asymmetric sinc-squared function to be properly implemented in KOPRA, PSG and ASIMUT, with discrepancies below $\sim 0.1 \%$ due to numerical approximations during normalization and interpolation processes.

These differences between KOPRA, ASIMUT and PSG are due to the complexities of the NOMAD instrumental features and all the subtle differences in the implementation of the radiative transfer calculations and numerical approximations. Being smaller than the measurement noise and the instrument characterization ambiguity, which are the most relevant uncertainties, do not have any significant impact during the data processing. Hence, the goal of having the same forward model generated by three independent algorithms has been successfully achieved, proving the same implementation of the NOMAD SO characterization into the radiative transfer codes. As shown in panels 1a and 2b of Figure S7, the overall agreement of the FM used in the retrievals is good, with the main spectral features such as the adjacent order addition and ILS convolution equally represented in all the simulations. The differences between these simulations are below the Level 1 NOMAD SO measurement noise with a mean ratio of the differences to the noise of ~ 0.05 . In addition, the slant H_2O column density values at 30 km obtained by PSG and KOPRA retrievals when using the same temperature and pressure shows relative differences below 0.07% .

The differences found in the FMs obtained from the fittings during the retrievals might be due to the different approaches used by the teams. In PSG and ASIMUT, the inversion is solved with the optimal estimation approach. Each spectrum (i.e. each tangent altitude) is considered as an independent measurement and a constant vertical profile representative of the exact location of the tangential observation is used as a priori (Villanueva et al. 2018, Vandaele et al. 2006). On the other hand, the RCP-KOPRA performs a global fit taking into account all the observations during the

atmospheric scan to produce the vertical profiles (Clarmann et al. 2003). Both approaches have costs and benefits depending on the type of observations to analyze (fast sampling with low latitudinal and longitudinal drifting or slow sampling with large latitudinal and longitudinal drifting on the planet's surface). In the case of RCP-KOPRA, the global fit allows a robust characterization of the profile, being sensitive to strong vertical gradients. However, the a priori used during the retrievals are profiles representative of the full atmospheric scan, and the pressure and temperature profiles must be under hydrostatic equilibrium. This way, possible horizontal inhomogeneities due to differences in the geographical location of the measurements during the scan are not taken into account. On the other hand, since PSG and ASIMUT consider each observation independently, they select the pressure and temperature representative for the exact location, although using a constant vertical profile during the inversion and not considering the contribution of the spectra from the layers above the observation may introduce uncertainties under conditions of strong vertical gradients.

Figure S1. Study of the saturation of absorption lines and example of H₂O vertical retrieved profile. Panel A shows the transmittance vertical profile at the core of the absorption line centered at 3779.1 cm⁻¹ (solid line) and at its wings (dotted and dashed lines) in the NOMAD diffraction order 168. Panels B and C show the ratio $R_{\lambda}(z)$ and its derivative respectively. The horizontal line in panel C shows the estimated transition altitude z^0 . Panel D shows the schematic of the methodology used to estimate the saturation of the absorption lines. Two curves are shown simulating unsaturated (blue) and saturated (red) absorption lines. The limit of the wings of the line is determined by $\Delta\lambda$. Panel E shows a typical H₂O vertical profile retrieved combining orders 134 (red) and 168 (orange). Horizontal dashed line indicates the transition altitude z^0 between the orders and gray shaded area shows the transition range where spectra of both orders are used during the inversion. Panels F and G show a side by side comparison of a water vapor profile and its vertical resolution respectively using the retrieval scheme presented here (blue) with Brines et al. 2023 (red). Profiles from panels E-G were obtained from the occultation 20200828_130241_1p0a_SO_A_E. Vertical resolution in panel G at 30 km is about 2 km (blue).

Figure S2. Typical diagnostics of the NOMAD measurement noise characterization with covariance matrices. Panel A shows the normalized covariance matrix ($\sigma_{ij}^2 / \sqrt{\sigma_{ii}^2 \sigma_{jj}^2}$) computed for order the 136 at 70-120 km during the solar occultation 20200827_112937_1p0a_SO_A_E. Panel B shows the comparison of the new (red) with the nominal NOMAD measurement noise (blue). Each red/blue curve corresponds to a different altitude. Panel C shows a NOMAD SO spectra at 96 km (blue) with the nominal noise (dashed gray), the standard deviation computed with the covariance matrix (dotted yellow) and the running standard deviation computed using a kernel of 20 pixels for reference (green).

Figure S3. Fitting (red line) of the average profiles at $L_s^1=240^\circ - 260^\circ$ (top panels), $L_s^2=260^\circ - 280^\circ$ (middle panels) and $L_s^3=280^\circ - 300^\circ$ (bottom panels) for MYs 34, 35 and 36 (panels A, B and C respectively) using the model from Chaffin et al. 2017. Shaded area of averaged profiles indicate the standard deviation of the average. Shaded area of the fitting profiles show the uncertainty of the fitting. The bad fitting below 50 km is due to the limitations of the model (see Text S4 for details). Panel D shows the estimated hydrogen flux for MYs 34 (light blue), 35 (orange) and 36 (green). Note that orange and green points are overlapped.

Figure S4. Seasonal variation of water vapor number density (cm^{-3}) in the southern hemisphere at 80 km for $L_s = 260^\circ - 300^\circ$ during MYs 34 and 35 (panels A and B) and at 100 km for the same period (panels C and D). Circles represent the observations presented in this work and triangles show data from Belyaev et al., 2021. Vertical red dashed line indicates $L_s = 265^\circ$.

Figure S5. Vertical profiles of the reference atmosphere used to generate the simulations for the forward model comparison. Profiles of temperature, pressure, H₂O and CO₂ Volume Mixing Ratios (VMR) are shown in panels A, B, C and D respectively. The profiles have been obtained from the Mars Planetary Climate Model for the location of the NOMAD observation 20180803_101739_1p0a_SO_A_I.

Figure S6. Simulated spectra generated with KOPRA (blue), PSG (red) and ASIMUT (yellow) during different stages of the NOMAD forward modeling. Panels 1a to 3a show the high resolution transmittance at 10 km without any filter function, after the grating function and after the order addition without AOTF respectively. Panels 1b to 3b show the same within a narrower spectral range. Panel 4 shows the normalized radiance at 100 km simulated with the AOTF filter (blue, red and yellow) and with a symmetric AOTF^{ref} (gray). Simulations in panels 1 to 4 were generated using arbitrary blaze and AOTF parameters (labeled as "test" parameters).

Figure S7. Panels 1a and 2a show the normalized forward model used for the fitting during a NOMAD data retrieval at 30 km for the diffraction order 134. The residuals between KOPRA, PSG and ASIMUT are shown in panels 1b and 2b. Forward models in panels 1 and 2 use the NOMAD characterization (labeled as "NOMAD" parameters).

Figure S8. Simulated water vapor latitudinal variation during $L_S^1=260 - 280^\circ$ (A1, B1) and $L_S^2=280 - 300^\circ$ (A2, B2) for MYs 34 (top) and 35 (bottom) for the NOMAD SO observations using assimilated data. The Open access to Mars Assimilated Remote Soundings (OpenMARS) assimilation combines the Mars Planetary Climate Model (PCM) Uk-spectral with several spacecraft data sets to provide a global reconstruction of the evolving water cycle constrained by several sets of temperature profiles, water vapor columns and profiles and dust column. Full details can be found in Holmes et al., 2022.

MY	LS	Total H flux ($\times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)
34	240-260	2.5 +/- 0.3
	260-270	2.3 +/- 0.4
	280-300	2.7 +/- 0.4
35	240-260	2.5 +/- 0.3
	260-280	3.2 +/- 0.5
	280-300	2.4 +/- 0.4
36	240-260	2.5 +/- 0.3
	260-280	3.2 +/- 0.5
	280-300	2.4 +/- 0.4

Table S1. Contribution to the hydrogen escape flux estimated with the model from Chaffin et al. 2017 for MYs 34, 35 and 36 during solar longitude ranges $L_5^1 = 240^\circ - 260^\circ$, $L_5^2 = 260^\circ - 280^\circ$ and $L_5^3 = 280^\circ - 300^\circ$.

References

- Belyaev, D. A., Fedorova, A. A., Trokhimovskiy, A., Alday, J., Montmessin, F., Korablev, O. I., ... & Shakun, A. V. (2021). Revealing a high water abundance in the upper mesosphere of Mars with ACS onboard TGO. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 48(10), e2021GL093411.
- Bhattacharyya, D., Clarke, J. T., Chaufray, J. Y., Mayyasi, M., Bertaux, J. L., Chaffin, M. S., ... & Villanueva, G. L. (2017). Seasonal changes in hydrogen escape from Mars through analysis of HST observations of the Martian exosphere near perihelion. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 122(11), 11-756.
- Brines, A., López-Valverde, M., Stolzenbach, A., Modak, A., Funke, B., Galindo, F., ... others (2023). Water vapor vertical distribution on Mars during perihelion season of my 34 and my 35 with ExoMars-TGO/NOMAD observations. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, e2022JE007273.
- Chaffin, M. S., Deighan, J., Schneider, N. M., & Stewart, A. I. F. (2017). Elevated atmospheric escape of atomic hydrogen from Mars induced by high-altitude water. *Nature geoscience*, 10(3), 174-178.
- Gordon, I. E., Rothman, L. S., Hargreaves, R. J., Hashemi, R., Karlovets, E. V., Skinner, F. M., ... & Yurchenko, S. N. (2022). The HITRAN2020 molecular spectroscopic database. *Journal of quantitative spectroscopy and radiative transfer*, 277, 107949.
- Holmes, J. A., Lewis, S. R., Patel, M. R., Alday, J., Aoki, S., Liuzzi, G., ... & Korablev, O. (2022). Global variations in water vapor and saturation state throughout the Mars Year 34 dusty season. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, 127(10), e2022JE007203.
- Jiménez-Monferrer, S., López-Valverde, M. Á., Funke, B., González-Galindo, F., Piccialli, A., García-Comas, M., ... & Bibring, J. P. (2021). CO₂ retrievals in the Mars daylight thermosphere from its 4.3 μm limb emission measured by OMEGA/MEx. *Icarus*, 353, 113830.
- Kuntz, M. (1997). A new implementation of the Humlicek algorithm for the calculation of the Voigt profile function. *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, 57(6), 819-824.
- Liuzzi, G., Villanueva, G. L., Mumma, M. J., Smith, M. D., Daerden, F., Ristic, B., et al. (2019). Methane on Mars: New insights into the sensitivity of CH₄ with the NOMAD/ExoMars spectrometer through its first in-flight calibration. *Icarus*, 321, 671-690. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icarus.2018.09.021>
- Ruyten, W. (2004). Comment on "A new implementation of the Humlicek algorithm for the calculation of the Voigt profile function" by M. Kuntz [JQSRT 57 (6)(1997) 819-824]. *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, 86(2), 231-233.
- Stiller, G. P., von Clarmann, T., Funke, B., Glatthor, N., Hase, F., Höpfner, M., & Linden, A. (2002). Sensitivity of trace gas abundances retrievals from infrared limb emission spectra to simplifying approximations in radiative transfer modelling. *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, 72(3), 249-280.
- Thomas, I. R., Aoki, S., Trompet, L., Robert, S., Depiesse, C., Willame, Y., ... & NOMAD Team. (2022). Calibration of NOMAD on ESA's ExoMars trace gas orbiter: Part 1-The solar occultation channel. *Planetary and Space Science*, 218, 105411.
- Vandaele, A. C., Lopez-Moreno, J. J., Patel, M. R., Bellucci, G., Daerden, F., Ristic, B., ... & NOMAD Team. (2018). NOMAD, an integrated suite of three spectrometers for the ExoMars trace gas mission: Technical description, science objectives and expected performance. *Space Science Reviews*, 214, 1-47.

Vandaele, A. C., De Mazière, M., Drummond, R., Mahieux, A., Neefs, E., Wilquet, V., ... & Bertaux, J. L. (2008). Composition of the Venus mesosphere measured by Solar Occultation at Infrared on board Venus Express. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, 113(E5).

Vandaele, A. C., Kruglanski, M., & De Mazière, M. (2006, May). Modeling and retrieval of atmospheric spectra using ASIMUT.

Villanueva, G. L., Smith, M. D., Protopapa, S., Faggi, S., & Mandell, A. M. (2018). Planetary Spectrum Generator: An accurate online radiative transfer suite for atmospheres, comets, small bodies and exoplanets. *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, 217, 86-104.

Villanueva, G. L., Smith, M. D., Protopapa, S., Faggi, S., & Mandell, A. M. (2018). Planetary Spectrum Generator: An accurate online radiative transfer suite for atmospheres, comets, small bodies and exoplanets. *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, 217, 86-104.

Villanueva, G. L., Liuzzi, G., Aoki, S., Stone, S. W., Brines, A., Thomas, I. R., ... & Vandaele, A. C. (2022). The deuterium isotopic ratio of water released from the Martian caps as measured with TGO/NOMAD. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 49(12), e2022GL098161.

Villanueva, G. L., Liuzzi, G., Faggi, S., Protopapa, S., Kofman, V., Fauchez, T., ... & Mandell, A. M. (2022). Fundamentals of the planetary spectrum generator. *Fundamentals of the Planetary Spectrum Generator. 2022 edition of the handbook by GL Villanueva et al. ISBN 978-0-578-36143-7*.

von Clarmann, V., Glatthor, N., Grabowski, U., Höpfner, M., Kellmann, S., Kiefer, M., ... & López-Puertas, M. (2003). Retrieval of temperature and tangent altitude pointing from limb emission spectra recorded from space by the Michelson Interferometer for Passive Atmospheric Sounding (MIPAS). *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 108(D23).